

Cost of Living: An Exploratory Study of Families of Chinnappampatti, Salem District

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Abstract

In 21st century, every person has the sole dream of earning and beautifying his life and for that, he indulges in the multiplicity of activities to make a sizeable earning and spend it on himself and family. It brings two important attitudes of human life — first, earning an income and second, spending it on the fulfillment of his needs. Some of these expenses are to meet the basic needs of life and some are done to fulfill his desires. The aggregate of all expenses done by a person on him and his family is called cost of living. It is requisite for every man, who wants to better his life, who wants to take any decision regarding his future, to maintain detail of each and every expense on his life, measure and analyze it. The main objective of this research is to ascertain the cost of living per family per year and the same per person per year. This study has attempted to contribute a simple and systematic method of ascertaining the cost of living.

Keywords: Cost of Living, expenses

Introduction

When one manufacturer produces the goods and services then, first of all, he ascertains the cost of each productive activity, then he aggregates each cost and calculates the total cost and tries to control the cost. The objective of a business organization is to the maxim: ze the profit by minimizing the cost.

As a manufacturer, every person wants to raise his living standard and increase his saving with the objective to minimize his cost of living. For this purpose, it is necessary for a person to know about the cost of living, to ascertain the cost of living and then control and minimize the cost of living.

Cost of living is the aggregate of sacrifices, expressed in monetary terms to fulfilling and increasing the living standard of a person and his family. According to the Columbia Encyclopedia, "Cost of living is the amount of money needed to buy the goods and services necessary to maintain a specific standard of living. The cost of living is closely tied to rates of inflation and deflation."

A person can determine the periodic saving, budgeting and planning the operations, control the cost and take sound financial decisions by ascertaining the cost of living.

Literature Review

At the outset, it is important to emphasize that traditional economics literature has overwhelmingly focused on constructing cost of living indices as a broad framework to measuring the changes in costs of consumption necessary to sustain a standard of living. This has also been the guiding theoretical framework of measuring consumer price indices (CPI) in several advanced economies like the US. The literature about the controversies of whether a cost of living index should be the guiding basis for the measurement of CPI is quite old and continues to this day (For a detailed discussion, see Triplett, 2000).

Interestingly, the concept of cost of living index is enmeshed with the broader idea of the standard of living, however vague a term that might be. As the related literature notes, the standard of living has been termed as an “elusive” and “complex” concept, more specifically from measuring it (Bennett, 1937). While there is no consensus on how exactly one defines a standard of living, it is intuitive to argue that no metric that measures standard of living in absolute terms can be convincing enough regarding its adequacy to reflect the entirety of the concept and hence the need to measure in relative terms. That being said, it is easier said than done because relative measures of standard of living also give rise to a whole host of methodological complications about relative comparisons and benchmarks which reduce their external validity.

Objective of the Study

Research can never be thought of without specifying its objectives. This research is also not an exception. Following are the objectives of this study:

- To estimate the cost of living per family per year and cost of living per person per year of different strata,
- To develop a methodology for determining the cost of living for a family and an individual.
- To find out the main elements of cost that is involved in the cost of living.
- To find out that, whether is the cost of living is influenced by an independent variable i.e., nature of the family, the income of the family and occupation of the family head.

Research Methodology

Sample Profile

To achieve the predetermined objectives of the study, it was decided to select a sample of 150 respondents from SALEM city. These respondents were selected at random and represented the 150 families of SALEM city. There was inconsistency in the information provided by four respondents; therefore these were not taken into consideration in the study. Hence 150 respondents were taken into consideration in the study. The samples were further classified into three strata; nature of the family, the income of the family and occupation of the family head.

Data Collection

To make this study scientific and specific, primary data have been taken into consideration. For the purpose of collecting primary data from 196 respondents; direct personal interview technique was used with the help of a questionnaire. This questionnaire had two sections namely, personal profile and expenditure pattern.

Statistical Tools

Data were analyzed with the help of statistical tools. The study used the following statistical tools: Mean, Percentage, Graphical Presentation, Statistical Parameter Limits and Large Sampling Test (Z Test).

Hypothesis

In this study, several statistical hypotheses were tested. The null hypothesis for Z- Test, at the level of confidence is used to find out that, is cost of living influenced by an independent variable i.e., nature of the family, the income of the family and occupation of the family head. The following statistical hypotheses were framed

1. The cost of living is not influenced by the nature of the family.
2. The cost of living is not influenced by the income of the family.
3. The cost of living is not influenced by the occupation of the family head.
4. To test these hypotheses, several sub-hypotheses were framed in this study.

Process of Ascertaining the Cost of Living

24 items of cost were identified for ascertaining the cost of living. These items were as follows: expenses incurred on food, clothing and footwear, residence, electricity, water bill, conveyance, communication, health, education and knowledge, news dailies and journals, seeking employment, entertainment, cosmetics, social commitment, social occasion, marriage, charity and offering, tour and travels, pocket money, pets, pursuing hobbies, addiction, other expenses and durables.

By simple observation, it was decided to curb some items of cost for further detail, analysis and interpretation. 24 items of cost of living were short listed into 13 items, looking to their relative importance, these are expenses incurred on food, clothing, residence, cosmetics, conveyance, communication, health, education, social, entertainment, pocket money, miscellaneous and durables.

The cost of living was classified into two broad categories (element of cost of living):

Cost of Consumables Cost of Durables

Out of the above 13 items, 12 items are part of the cost of consumables, and one is the cost of durables. Cost of durables includes both long term and short term durables. The list of 23 items of durables was identified such as- crockery, television, venire, utensils, A.C., etc. By GAAP the following formula was used for converting the cost of durables per year:

(Cost of Durables— Scrape Value) / Expected Life of the durables in the years. After getting total cost of consumables and cost of durables Per year, we have calculated both per family per year. The following formula was used for fulfilling the above objectives:

Cost of consumable per family per year = Total cost of consumables per year / No. of families (150)

Cost of durables per family per year = Total cost of durables per year / No. of families (150)

After that, in this study, we have calculated the cost of living per person per year. The following formula was to be used:

Cost of living per person per year = Cost of Living per family per year / Average size of the family

Effect of Col on Wages

Although COL indices capture the cost of a sample of goods and services in various locations, it does not necessarily mean that businesses will (or should) adjust in a straight forward and linear manner. For one, not all goods and services are affected by local cost differences. For example,

online purchases made through national retailers will generally not be affected (or have minimally different effects, such as from shipping costs or tax rates) by local cost conditions. Another example would be costs associated with a vacation stay outside of the area. Different employees within a firm do not consume the same basket of goods. The consumption of employees with higher incomes may be expected to contain a larger proportion of non-local goods and services—such as luxury items, vacations, high-end durable goods (e.g., cars), and savings—which are less affected by COL levels. However, those earning lower wages will be more dependent on goods at the local level that reflects the COL differences and will have fewer substitution options (e.g., a higher percentage of income is spent on food and housing) regarding their discretionary spending.⁵ The proportion of income spent on such items as rent (local) and food should thus decline with the level of income. In this case, the effect of COL on wages should diminish at higher pay levels. Hence, wages will be more sensitive to the COL differences at lower wage levels. Thus, even if a company desires to keep someone's spending power constant across two locations, the extent to which they need to adjust salary levels should decrease as wages increase. We would, therefore, expect, for example, that adjustments for COL will be greater for a housekeeping position than for a rooms manager. It becomes important, then, to establish the nature of the relationship between wages and COL.

Conclusion and Suggestions

There are two major activities of a person, first to earn income and second to spend this income as expenses for fulfilling the human needs. Some expenses are regular and some are irregular. The aggregate of all expenses done by a person on him and his family is called cost of living. This study found some advantages of ascertaining the cost of living, such as—determination of periodical saving, budgeting and planning of activities, cost control, day to day application of family plans and help in taking sound financial decisions.

This study reveals that there is two important elements of cost of living, i.e., cost of consumables and cost of durables. Cost of consumables further divided into twelve items of cost, these were: expenses incurred on food, clothing, residence, cosmetics, conveyance, communication, health, education, social, entertainment, pocket money and miscellaneous.

The cost of consumables has the major share in the cost of living approximately 93%. The cost of living per family per year, cost of consumables per family per year and cost of durables per family/ per year comes out to be approximately Rs. 2.00 lakhs, Rs.1.90 lakhs and Rs..15 thousand. The cost of living per person per year cost of consumables per person per year and cost of durables per person per year comes out to be Rs. 43 thousand, Rs.40 thousand and Rs.3 thousand.

This study also tested the hypotheses that, is cost of living influenced by the nature of the family, the income of the family and occupation of the family head. By survey results, it can be concluded that there are insignificant differences between the cost of living per family per year of families headed by businessman, professional, employee and other occupation. It means the cost of living is not influenced by the occupation of the family head.

This study also concludes that there is the significant difference between the cost of living per family per year of families having the different level of income (below 1 lakh, 1-3 lakhs, 3-5 lakhs and five lakhs and above). It means the cost of living is influenced by the income of the family and as income increases cost of living per family per year also increases. This shows as income increases, the living standard of respective families also increases.

This study reveals that there is the significant difference between the cost of living per family per year of nuclear families and semi-joint families and nuclear and joint families, but there is the insignificant difference between the cost of living per family per year of semi-joint and joint families.

By findings above and survey experience, this study has identified following certain significant areas and suggestions, which need to the attention of the relevant agencies namely; the Government, Professional Accountant, family and an individual and the researcher of this field.

- The survey result reveals that the cost of living per person per year is minimum in joint families as compared to semi-joint and nuclear families. So that, it is suggested that, if a person wants to minimize his cost of living, he should live in a joint family.
- A person should give more attention towards rational spending on consumables, because the cost of consumables is a vital area and cover approximately 93% of the total cost of living.
- It is suggested that an individual also plans for the domestic expenditure after attaining his age of superannuation for at least 20 more years of his living with the same standard of living for each of the 20 years and use discounted cash flow approach to find the present value of futuristic needs of family through an appropriate technique provision be done during his active earning period to generate this fund.
- It is suggested that a separate study is undertaken to analyze the cost of consumables, cost of durables and domestic financial planning.
- This study also suggests that there should be a systematic domestic accounting system to ascertain the cost of living per family per year and per person per year.

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